

Resettlement Aspirations Versus Realities: Exploring the Expectations of Syrian Refugees in Lebanon

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For the most vulnerable, resettlement is often a synonym for hope (Coquelet, 2017), particularly in a no-asylum country² like Lebanon, experiencing complex economic, financial, social, and health crises since 2019. Hence, being a refugee in Lebanon, means that vulnerabilities that derive from the displacement status are amplified (Brun & Maalouf, 2022). In this context, a sizeable number of Syrian refugees in Lebanon (27%)³ aspire for resettlement to a third country primarily for better living conditions, to join family members who are already living abroad, or to pursue their education (UNHCR, 2023a).

Studies abound on post-resettlement experiences of asylum seekers and Syrian refugees in third countries, mainly the United States, Canada, and Australia (Dennler, 2021 & Mzayek, 2019 & Omar, 2023 & Smith et al., 2020). These studies, however, focus on resettlement as a final destination. Indeed, people who resettled, despite their life improvements, still face new kinds of uncertainty, ambiguities, and other unique challenges related to resettlement that are somewhat undertheorized (Milkie et al., 2020).

In light of this, this brief is dedicated to addressing a specific phenomenon highlighting the root causes of the gap between pre-resettlement expectations of Syrian refugees in Lebanon and post-resettlement realities.⁴ It aims to provide insights into the hopeful intention toward resettlement among Syrian refugees in Lebanon, and how three main factors - the socioeconomic, legal, and administrative - shape this hope. In this context “hope”, signifies “engagements with the future in a context of protracted displacement” (Brun, 2016). Subsequently, this brief delves into various post-resettlement experiences through the perspective of emerging challenges.

Unraveling the Interplay: Vulnerabilities of Refugees and the Sentiment of Stuckness

The economic situation of Syrian refugees in Lebanon has steadily deteriorated since 2019, when over two-thirds of Syrian refugees did not have the economic capacity to afford the minimum essential items needed to survive (VASyR, 2023). In June 2021, 49% of Syrian refugee families were food insecure, and about two-thirds of the families had to limit food portion sizes or reduce the number of meals consumed per day (UNHCR, 2021). Additionally, UNHCR’s latest Protection Monitoring results reveal that 35% of refugees have reduced their access to healthcare, and 33%

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² The Lebanese government considers the only durable solution available for “displaced Syrians” in Lebanon is their safe return to Syria, and the resettlement to be only a ‘partial solution’ because it is available to very few (LCRP, 2023a).

³ Jordan has the first highest percentage of those hoping to return within five years (38%), and Lebanon has the second highest percentage (25%), followed by Iraq (11%).

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cannot afford essential medicine (UNHCR, 2023b). Consequently, the immediate needs of refugees have become more pronounced, demanding increased financial aid and essential provisions such as shelter, food, water, electricity, and fuel. The hostile economic conditions were amplified during the COVID-19 pandemic. Back then, many families lost their livelihoods due to having to stay at home and to businesses closing down (Brun & Maalouf, 2022). This heightened dependency on aid as a direct consequence, followed by debt and lastly work (Refugees-Partners, 2021).

The humanitarian response to the refugee crisis in Lebanon has increasingly relied on cash assistance under the Lebanon Crisis Response Plan (LCRP) to support Syrian refugees living in Lebanon (AUB & Cameleon, 2020). However, this approach predominantly emphasizes short-term aid to sustain and support refugees, particularly in light of the pandemic and economic crisis, potentially overlooking the underlying conditions that cause prolonged displacement (Brun & Maalouf, 2022). However, funding to Lebanon over the years fell short of response needs (figure 1). On average, Lebanon's donor support was half of what was needed and requested (Mahdi, 2020).

Figure 1: Funding received by Lebanon for 2019 including the period January-September in USD compared to response needs (LCPS, 2020)

Source: Mahdi, D. (2020, June). Supporting the Future of Syria and the Region: The Lebanese Government’s Redundant Commitments and Slow Progress. *The Lebanese Center for Policies Studies*. <https://api.lcps-lebanon.org/content/uploads/files/policy53.pdf>

According to the LCRP 2023 Q3 funding update, funds covering 29% of the \$3.6 billion appeal were made available. This includes \$634.1 million received between January and September 2023, plus \$395.5 million in carry-over and multi-year funds received in 2022. This leaves a 71% gap of \$2.6 billion (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Q3 Funding update of the Lebanon Crisis Response Plan 2023 as of 7th of November 2023

Furthermore, the Lebanese State's ad-hoc policies concerning Syrian refugees' legal status heightened refugees' uncertainties, with only 17% of Syrian refugees holding a legal residency in 2022 (VASyR, 2023). This led refugees to engage in informal employment, especially in agriculture and construction (Brun et al., 2021), exacerbating existing socio-economic vulnerabilities (Kikano et al., 2021).

Thus, with the Lebanese state's unwillingness to allow refugees to socially integrate because of broader socio-political attitudes ("Better Policies and Laws...", 2023), refugees' feelings of despair are heightened in a depoliticised humanitarian approach (Brun & Maalouf, 2022). In this context, the intersectionality of various different types of vulnerabilities, exacerbate refugees' sense of exclusion and feeling of being place bound in an endless present.

This sense of stuckness (Fakhoury, 2024) may lead refugees to only travel through their imagination (Cangi`a & Zittoun, 2020) or make a dangerous journey to Europe (UNHCR, 2018). Between 2020 and 2022, a growing number of Syrian refugees sought informal ways to flee Lebanon by attempting to leave irregularly by sea, often with the help of smugglers and human traffickers (OCHA, 2023). The number of Syrians trying to cross into Europe doubled in 2022, 92,472 compared with the previous year's 46,395 (Petillo, 2023). In Lebanon, according to UNHCR, between January and November 2022, 4,296 people attempted the journey, compared to 1,570 in 2021, 794 in 2020 and 270 in 2019, with 62 per cent of them were Syrian. Also, between 160 and 170 individuals having departed from Lebanon are reported missing or dead in 2022 alone compared to a combined number of 64 in 2015 (OCHA, 2023).

Therefore, refugees find themselves in a state of anticipation, awaiting the opportunity for resettlement as their only solution, "but not without some misgivings" (El Shaarawi, 2015). Consequently, this sets the stage for an exploration of the profound influence of the "feeling of stuckness" of the Syrian refugees in Lebanon, on their future expectations and encounters when it comes to aspiring resettlement.

Refugee Resettlement: Navigating Ways, Time, and Hope

According to the *Eighth Regional Survey on Syrian Refugees’ Perceptions & Intentions on Return to Syria* published by UNHCR in May 2023, “an increasing number of respondents compared to last year’s survey indicated a hope to move to a third country through resettlement”. The survey’s findings highlight a correlation between refugees’ ability to fulfill basic needs in their host country and their aspiration to move to a third country (UNHCR, 2023a). For instance, a fieldwork conducted in Tripoli in 2020, predating the COVID-19 lockdown, as part of the Horizon 2020-TRAFIG project, revealed that many households in Tripoli announced their pursuit of resettlement abroad regardless of limited opportunities. Also, many families simultaneously desire resettlement in another country while also prioritising the cohesion of relational networks. For some, they would leave immediately if granted the opportunity: *“Even if I go to China, it is not a problem. The most important thing is to find a good life for the children”* (Forster & Abdalkader, 2021).

Moreover, these aspirations are significantly shaped and amplified by other factors including awareness about the overall resettlement process. Generally, Syrian refugees’ awareness about resettlement programs differs depending on several components, such as their registration with UNHCR, place of residence, social network, access to social media, and surrounding by well-informed actors - organisations’ staff, for example (Coquelet, 2017). However, this awareness shrinks when encountering barriers to accessing organizations that provide resettlement or complementary pathways. These barriers could arise from several issues, such as the unavailability of public information on resettlement, difficulties in reaching UNHCR’s offices during the Covid-19 lockdowns, and their lack of familiarity with resettlement eligibility criteria and procedures (Brun & Maalouf, 2022).

Hence, all these factors affect refugees’ understanding of the resettlement process, perceived by many as highly ambiguous. Most Syrian refugees perceive resettlement programs as lacking clarity and transparency (El Diaf et al., 2021), with the role of UNHCR in this context remains vague for them (Coquelet, 2017).

As a result, refugees tend to develop unverified assumptions about submission categories or criteria, the possibility of choosing a resettlement country, and the right to family reunification (Coquelet, 2017). These expectations are very “powerful” and can be a source of hope or, in cases where resettlement is challenging, a source of suffering.

Even people who qualify for resettlement are subject to uncertainty and prolonged waiting, in many cases for years (Mzayek, 2019), throughout the long and complex application process, fostering a sense of inability to feel secure and satisfied in the present (Dennler, 2021).

Having established the context surrounding resettlement uncertainties, the last section of this brief investigates some experiences of resettled refugees and assesses the extent of fulfillment of their aspirations following resettlement.

"Is Resettlement the Cure for Refugee Vulnerabilities?"

Many Syrian refugees experience life improvements once they resettle in third countries, where they find new homes and are provided with resettlement assistance (Mzayek, 2019), which creates some hope for stability. At the same time, these refugees encounter a myriad of challenges in the post-resettlement process, particularly in host countries, where cultural, religious and social obstacles are intertwined, such as Canada and the USA. For example, some Syrian families resettled in the United States faced a tough time dealing with both the culture and the language, causing issues with their finances, health and identity (Mzayek, 2019). The same challenges are faced by Syrian refugees who resettled in Canada who do not know English or French (Houle, 2019). As a result, miscommunication because of the language barrier could cause a person to lose their job (Mzayek, 2019).

Also, during the first few months of resettlement, all resettled Syrian refugees are provided medical care, housing and financial help through the government or private sponsors⁵ (Elcioglu, 2021). Following this, Syrian refugee families are expected to survive on their own (Mzayek, 2019). Consequently, they could be obliged to spend their savings if they do not find job opportunities quickly and in light of the lengthy waiting period concerning work permits (Mzayek, 2019).

When it comes to the social status of refugees, vulnerable groups, such as mothers or widows, face increased struggles, such as having additional responsibilities towards their children's future (Omar, 2022). Also, young Syrian adults who resettled in the United States with university credentials faced obstacles in transferring and pursuing higher education, while others were unable to pursue a university degree due to financial problems (Mzayek, 2019).

Furthermore, the absence of a support system provided by an extended family network or the challenges in imagining themselves as part of the new community compounds their struggles (Omar, 2023). Finally, disparities in norms and values between the country of origin and the host country introduce additional complexity, requiring Syrian refugees to navigate to adapt to new cultural norms (Omar, 2023).

At the end, it seems that resettlement is not the end of the "waiting phase" as refugees expect; however, building a life in the resettled country also requires a new mode of "waiting" until different goals are achieved (Omar, 2022).

Conclusion

This brief has explored the intertwined sources and implications of the resettlement aspirations of Syrian refugees. In the first phase, we unraveled how the intersectionality of the different types of vulnerabilities intertwined with the different policies of exclusion Syrian refugees are dealing with. This causes Syrian refugees to feel stuck in Lebanon and nurtures hopes that resettlement could be a

⁵ Private sponsorship has become a primary way that refugees access resettlement to Canada. Key in this program are the private Canadians who volunteer their money, time, and labor to sponsor and support refugees (Elcioglu, 2021).

way to establish a stable new life, regain autonomy, achieve self-reliance, and integrate into a society that respects their rights. However, these hopeful expectations are often amplified by rumors in their communities, misunderstandings, and a lack of information, leading to misinterpretations of the challenges they may encounter post-resettlement. Consequently, such discrepancies between expectations and realities can result in disappointment and dissatisfaction among resettled individuals. After all, how does one measure the end of refugees’ journeys and waiting?

To conclude, it is crucial to build a deeper understanding of the following questions:

- How effectively has the Global Compact on Refugees addressed the challenges of resettlement, and what are the key areas that still require attention?
- In what ways can the UNHCR enhance its role within the Global Compact on Refugees to better facilitate and promote successful resettlement initiatives for displaced populations?
- To what extent the resettlement in third countries could create an identity crisis for the refugees? And how do they face or overcome them?

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